

Supplementary Figure 2. Conservation analysis of ORF1 and conservation and stability analysis of 134aa. (A) Conservation analysis of circSLC41A1 ORF1 among different species; (B) Conservation analysis of circSLC41A1-134aa among different species; (C) Secondary structure prediction of circSLC41A1-134aa. Upper panel: Conf score ranges from 0 to 9. The larger the score, the more stable about amino acid structure. Helix represents α -helix in red, strand represents β -sheet in blue, and coil represents random coil in black. Lower panel: The lower part indicates that the more negative the curve part is, the more stable about amino acid structure is.

1.3 Tables S1-S4

Table S1. Oligonucleotide sequence

Name	Sequence (5'-3')
circSLC41A1-siRNA	Sense: CAUCGUGCAGGUGUCCAUTT Antisense: AUGGAACACCUGCACGAUGTT
SRSF1-siRNA	Sense: GCCCAGAAGUCCAAGUUAUTT Antisense: AUAACUUGGACUUCUGGGCTT
miR-9820-5p mimics	Sense: GAGGAGGAGGGAAGAAAGGCU Antisense: CCUUUCUUCCCUCUCCUCUU
miR-9830-5p inhibitor	AGCCUUUCUUCCCUCUCCUC
Negative control	Sense: UUCUCCGAACGUGUCACGUTT Antisense: ACGUGACACGUUCGGAGAATT
NC inhibitor	CAGUACUUUUGUGUAGUACAA

Table S2. The information of primers

Gene	Acc. No.	Primer (5'-3')	function
ssc-circSLC41A1 -E2	ENSSSCG 00000020783	F: GAGGTGGTGGTGATTGAGTCT R: GCCCTCTTAGGTGGCTCTT	PCR & qRT-PCR
GAPDH	AF017079	F: GGACTCATGACCACGGTCCAT R: TCAGATCCACAACCGACACGT	qRT-PCR
miR-9820-5p	NR_128505.1	F: GCCGAGGAGGAGGAGGGAA R: CTCAACTGGTGTCTGTGGA CTCAACTGGTGTCTGTGGAGTCGG CAATTCAGTTGAGCCTTTC	qRT-PCR
SRSF1	NM_001038007.1	F: CGGCGAGTTTGAGAAGGTA R: GCAGAACGACAAACCATCC	qRT-PCR
SLC41A1	NM_001243667.1	F: ATCCGCATCCCTAGTGACC R: GCCCTCTTAGGTGGCTCTT	qRT-PCR

Table S3.**The binding site of miR-9820-5p and ssc-circSLC41A1/SRSF1**

Name	Region	Binding site sequence (5'-3')
ssc-circSLC41A1- WT	954~984nt	...GCAAGTGCTGTTCCCCT TCCTCCT GGCAGG...
ssc-circSLC41A1- MUT	954~984nt	...GCAAGTGCTGTTCCCCT AGGAGGA GGCAGG...
SRSF1-WT	1355~1401nt	...ATTACAGTATCTAACATTTTGCC TCCTCTTTT TTGGTTTTGCTGGTT...
SRSF1-MUT	1355~1401nt	...ATTACAGTATCTAACATTTTGCC CAAGACCCT TTGGTTTTGCTGGTT...

Note: 1nt represents pig chromosome 9 66497541 at SLC41A1. 1nt represents pig chromosome 12 34279853 at SRSF1.

Table S4. FISH probe sequence

Name	Sequence	Probe type
ssc-circSLC41A1	5'-CTGTATGGAACACCTGCACGATGTCCAG-3'	DIG
miR-9820-5p	5'-AGCCTTTCTTCCCTCCTCCTC-3'	DIG